

Development of a virtual reality application for disaster preparedness training in St. Dominic College of Asia

Pauline Arvian R. Hala

School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of Asia

pahala@sdca.edu.ph

Abstract

This project study aimed to develop a mobile-based Virtual Reality (VR) application for Disaster Preparedness Training at St. Dominic College of Asia. It used the Unity real-time application for the VR simulation, Blender for creating 3D models and infrastructure, Photoshop CS6, and C# programming language. The systems proof of concept was shown through fire, earthquake, and typhoon scenarios, while at the same time suggesting at the end its hazards and mitigation strategies. The study was verified, tested, and evaluated by 100 respondents consisting of 30 students from Higher Education, 20 students from Senior High School and 10 students from Basic Education, 32 employees consisting of Teacher and Administrative Staff on different sectors, five (5) IT experts from St. Dominic College of Asia and three (3) representatives from City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (CDRRMO). The developed application was proven acceptable in terms of reliability, usability, and portability as it was rated "excellent" by the respondents composed of students, employees, IT experts, and representatives from the City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office.

Keywords: *Virtual Reality, disaster management, training, simulation.*

Introduction

Natural disasters such as typhoons, floods, and earthquakes are commonly experienced in the Philippines that lead to a devastating event if they occurred in a vulnerable area inhabited by humans (Jha et al., 2018). Being prepared and knowing what to do during calamities and disasters in a specific area is called disaster preparedness. In the Philippines, there is a government organization named "National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council" (NDRRMC) (NDRRMP, 2011), a council which implements a risk reduction strategy called the "National Disaster Risk Reduction Project (NDRRP)" that includes four disaster areas: "Disaster Prevention and Mitigation; Preparedness, Response, Rehabilitation, and Recovery," which refers to the NDRRMC organization.

The campus of St. Dominic College of Asia comprises three contiguous buildings with no wide area for the participants to standby during drills. Prevention and preparedness in such natural calamities are one of the major concerns of the institution. The rules set by the NDRRMC for planning in Disaster Risk Reduction and Management are always being followed. Even though the institution conducts seminars, trainings, drills, and disseminates posters and advertisements to teach disaster preparedness to all the members of the community there are still comments from the local government DRRMC of Bacoor City, during and after the drills are conducted. The question is, are those kinds of medium in disseminating information with disaster preparedness enough to train the citizen on what to do during these natural disasters or calamities? Therefore, implementing simulation through another medium in virtual reality has been foreseen as a solution to strengthen the knowledge of the institution in disaster preparedness.

Through the rise of the technology-based approach, the training of learners in disaster preparedness is being slowly presented through Virtual Reality (VR). There are multiple environments that appear promising to be maximized to bridge the gap that has been existing in the commonly established training format (Hsu et al., 2013). The immersive nature of virtual reality training offers abundance in information for each of the situations presented. Hsu et al. (2013) said that Virtual Reality when used for practice offers a different setting that is not easily replicated in the physical space, and aside from that virtual reality presents robust cost effectivity and advantages when compared to large-scale exercises which may be the reason it is slowly being applied globally to training. Through other mediums such as popular media, phones, and television, the virtual reality has long been presented (Steuer, 1992).

In the current training day, the virtual reality is already used in different implementations, such as fire exercises, flight simulations, driving simulations, and numerous other simulations for training purposes (Silcox, 2019). The training students receive is the equivalent of the practice they require in facing emergencies, earning them the abilities. The training of students to face emergencies requires the mastery of several skills and abilities that need practice and through Virtual Reality, it can enhance these skill sets (Silcox, 2019). Facing real life simulated emergencies causes and exposes the learners to danger in the initial state of training; hence, it should be avoided. Instead, training should be provided in a controlled setting that can mimic real-life situation as closely as possible, and through virtual reality, this is attainable with less cost (Mossel et al., 2015). According to Mossel et al. (2015), “virtual reality (VR) simulations are some alternative practice environments for safety education”. Through virtual reality, learners and trainees alike gain experience closest to the real scenario without facing dangerous conditions (Isleyen & Duzgun, 2019).

There are abundance of teaching and training tools for academic activities, but despite the potential and acceptance of these tools for their academic value, there is still a gap of acceptance and content with the potential of usability of this virtual reality software when it is focused on delivering a structured disaster preparedness training that would make the training fun and enjoyable for its users (Ma et al., 2014). To increase the mastery of a skill, it is often a requisite that the skill in question is repeated deliberately if this precise method is executed in the physical space, exhaustion, limitation of the space provided and cost is considered in the design (Andreatta et al., 2010). The focus of the current practice is fully utilizing cost and other resources allotted to the training (Prakash & Rao, 2015). In virtual reality, replicating this method can be cost-efficient and can be provided through a medium that is always readily available for the students and users to train at their own pace, until the said mastery of the skills is achieved (Ma et al., 2014).

Methodology

Project Design

The developed system, which is a virtual reality application for disaster preparedness training at St. Dominic College of Asia has used Unified Modeling Language (UML) - Use-Case Diagram. This is to determine the desired outcome in the style of the system and to compose a detailed interaction within the system and the user.

Figure 1 Use case diagram of the application

Figure 1 presents the UML-Use Case Diagram. The user reaches out in the main menu area at the start of the system. The user can step around the environment to decide whether to start the simulator scenario, read the instructions or quit the game. The Main Menu loads a series of scenarios. Afterwards, the user needs to choose within the building selection and floor selection to load the randomized tasks with schemes that the player can be played.

Scenarios such as fire-breakout, typhoons, and earthquakes might intrude at any scenario based on scenario selection. Once the scenario has come out within the simulation, it will load time to imitate real-life scenario emergency training drill for the player to do the practices and follow the emergency action plan.

System Flowchart

Figure 2 illustrates the flow of the system. When the application is initialized, it directs the player in the main menu. The player must choose a scenario from the main menu, which categorizes the scenario in a specific hazard such as the Fire-Breakout, Typhoon, and Earthquake. Once the user has selected a scenario, the player will now select what building number to enter. Building number selection depends on the preferred building number that the player or the user always interacts. The building selection comprises the buildings namely: GD-1 for Higher Education, GD-2 for Basic Education, and GD-3 for Senior High School. After choosing the building number, the user now has to choose what floor to go. Once the user chose a floor, the user will be directed in the environment; and if a mission will be loaded, the mission is to collect a piece of infographic images pertaining to the basic practices in emergency precautions. The user must collect the images then the chosen scenario will be loaded. The user needs to follow the direction of the arrow pertaining to the shortest path of the evacuation route. When the player passed through the main evacuation plan, an emergency precautions window will prompt in the game result to give knowledge to the user for a certain emergency scenario.

Figure 2 System flowchart

Project Development

Development Paradigm

The researcher used the spiral model as a development paradigm in developing the system. Because the spiral model combines iterative development, and waterfall model (Boehm, 1988). The spiral model allows for incremental releases of a system such as a game (Hvass et al., 2017). Since this project is a game development project intended for Virtual Reality Simulation games for disaster preparedness, the developer followed the stages of the spiral model and process and begin each stage after it has completed the previous stage.

Figure 3 Spiral model diagram (Boehm, 1988)

Testing Procedure

Test Case Form

To ensure the accuracy of the system, series of tests were conducted for each user type and module. The study used the actual scenario at the SDCA evacuation plane. The plan was re-executed to validate that the issues are resolved. The researcher used usability, reliability, and portability as the test criteria.

TEST CASE ID		UC Reference	
Objective			
Assumptions/Preconditions:			
Actions	Expected Results		
1			
2			
3			
Status		Severity	Priority

Table 1 Test case form

The table includes the following information:

1. Test Case ID which is a unique number that identifies the test case;
2. UC Reference which states the reference in the requirement document that served as the basis for that case;
3. The objective which describes the test case to be performed;
4. Assumption/Preconditions are the criteria that need to be fulfilled before the test procedure can be run;
5. Actions which indicate the steps needed to run the test case;
6. Expected Output which defines the anticipated test result; and
7. Actual Results which show if the application had passed or failed the test case with appropriate severity and priority marks also described.

Test cases execution and results for each condition are recorded, and these indicate if whether it is passed or failed. A passed condition means that actual results are like expected results. A failed condition means that the system experienced bugs or errors, and there are some steps taken to replicate the error encountered then indicate the severity classification and priority levels.

Evaluation Procedure

To determine the acceptability of the system, the evaluation procedure involved 100 respondents; 30 students from Higher Education, 20 students from Senior High School, and 10 students from Basic Education, 32 employees consisting of Teachers and Administrative Staff of different sectors, five (5) IT experts from St. Dominic College of Asia, and three (3) representatives from City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office (CDRRMO). The study adopted the ISO 25010 evaluation instrument to check the functionality and portability of the system using a 5-point Likert scale.

The ratings indicated in the full research show the interpreted rating scale of “Excellent” being the highest and “Poor” being the lowest. To determine the result of the evaluation a formula below of “mean” was used.

In the formula, the mean was obtained by computing the sum of all the responses and dividing the result by the number of respondents. By getting the result of the mean, scores were determined based on the scale range interpretation as follows: 4.51-5.00 for “Excellent”, 3.51-4.50 for “Very Good”, 2.51-3.50 for “Good”, 1.51-2.50 for “Fair”, and 1.00-1.50 for “Poor”.

Results and Discussion

The results were obtained from the operation and testing procedure undertaken by the researcher.

Table 2 Test results

Test On	Results
1. Main Menu	Can successfully move around the vicinity using VR Box
2. Scenario Selection	Can easily choose a scenario because it provides an engaging design.
3. Building Selection	Can easily select a building choice
4. Floor Selection	Can easily choose floor destination from the floor selection
5. Fire-breakout Scenario	Can successfully play a fire-breakout scenario. Can easily interact and walk around using Bluetooth controller.
6. Typhoon Scenario	Can successfully play the Typhoon scenario. Can easily interact and walk around using Bluetooth controller.
7. Earthquake Scenario	Can successfully play Earthquake scenario. Can easily interact and walk around using Bluetooth controller.
8. Game Result	Can easily display Disaster Preparedness precautions on the scenario.
9. Quit Game/Exit	Can easily quit and exit using VR Box pointer.

For each item in Table 2, the application was installed on devices that were available to the proponent at the time. The tested items were running on the device and executed the simulation. The proponent simulated on how the user will go through each selection of floor building and scenarios for each disaster to test if the application properly displays objectives, and the path to the exit or the designated assembly point was followed and upon reaching the end objectives will trigger the event to show the results. The test case forms were consolidated to compile results for each scenario and location of the simulation to minimize redundancy.

Project Evaluation

Based on the evaluation conducted on the developed system entitled “The Development of Virtual Reality Application for Disaster Preparedness Training at St. Dominic College of Asia”, it gained an overall mean of 4.43 interpreted as “Excellent”.

Reliability Test Results

Reliability tests were done in two phases which is the non-functional testing and then the regression testing occurred. All test cases were completed in Phase 1. Nonetheless, 2.2 % of test cases failed and just 97.8% of test cases passed. This data shows that even though very high on the passed tests since the simulation is for evacuation, 100% reliability is needed to be achieved fully; hence, deeming the first phase is not successful. The reliability live test incident log includes all the defects found when conducting the testing of reliability. Following the first phase, the code fixes and revisions were to implement corrections to the failed areas. After the fixes were applied, all test cases were again executed in Phase 2 as the regression test to check if the code and fixes applied were working and did not affect other parts of the simulation. In the second phase, 100 percent of test cases, where a passing mark of 100% was obtained and executed. This means the reliability testing is successful.

Table 3 Respondents' mean rating for the reliability of the project

Reliability Criteria	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Maturity	4.45	Excellent
2. Fault tolerance	4.46	Excellent
3. Reliability compliance	4.34	Excellent
<i>Average</i>	4.41	Excellent

Table 3 shows the result of the respondents' ratings for the reliability test of the system. The result from the conducted evaluation obtained an average of 4.41, which is interpreted as “Excellent”.

Table 4 Respondents' mean rating for the usability of the project

Usability Criteria	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Understandability	4.50	Excellent
2. Learnability	4.42	Excellent
3. Operability	4.48	Excellent
<i>Average</i>	4.46	Excellent

Table 4 shows the result of the respondents' ratings for the usability test of the system. The total mean result from the conducted evaluation obtained an average of 4.46, which is interpreted as “Excellent”.

Table 5 Respondents' mean rating for the portability of the project

Portability Criteria	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Adaptability	4.34	Excellent
2. Installability	4.40	Excellent
3. Portability	4.48	Excellent
<i>Average</i>	4.40	Excellent

Table 5 shows the result of the respondents' ratings for the portability test of the system. The total mean result from the conducted evaluation obtained an average of 4.40, which is interpreted as “Excellent”.

Table 6 Overall mean rating of the project

Overall Criteria	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Maturity	4.45	Excellent
2. Fault tolerance	4.46	Excellent
3. Reliability compliance	4.34	Excellent
4. Understandability	4.50	Excellent
5. Learnability	4.42	Excellent
6. Operability	4.48	Excellent
7. Adaptability	4.34	Excellent
8. Installability	4.40	Excellent
9. Portability	4.48	Excellent
<i>Average</i>	4.43	Excellent

Table 6 shows the overall mean rating of the project which resulted in 4.43 interpreted as “Excellent”. The test was conducted using three categories: Reliability, Usability, and Portability.

In terms of reliability, the criterion of fault tolerance was able to get the highest rating of 4.46 which is as excellent. Fault tolerance indicates that the system does not terminate despite errors or bugs encountered while the reliability got the lowest rating of 4.34 still an excellent rating that pertains to the overall reliability of the system.

In terms of the usability of the system, operability got the highest rating of 4.48 which is interpreted as “Excellent”. Operability indicates that the system is easy to use while learnability got the lowest rating of 4.42 but still an “Excellent” rating that to the capability of the system to enable the user to learn how to use it.

Then in terms of portability, the developed system was able to get a high rating of 4.48 which is interpreted as “Excellent”. The rating was reflected in the overall portability of the system. While adaptability obtained the lowest rating of 4.34 described as “Excellent”, this pertains that the system can run on various android devices that meet the requirements.

Overall, from the conducted survey it garnered a qualitative description of “Excellent” which shows that the developed system was able to meet the subjected requirements for the system. By analyzing the scores and average from the given results, the users were able to use the system properly and well acknowledged the objectives set by the system.

The purpose of the study is to develop an Android-based Virtual Reality application for Disaster Preparedness Simulation at St. Dominic College of Asia. The system aims to promote knowledge in preparing for such a disaster that may be experienced inside a building. The application allows a virtual reality environment.

It also shows the overall mean rating of the project, which resulted in 4.43 interpreted as “Excellent”. The test was conducted using that tries to mimic the same environment of the target

institution. The infrastructure as well as the floor plan was initiated to simulate the evacuation route that is being practiced during an emergency drill by the people inside the institution.

The common disasters simulated were the Fire-breakout, Typhoon, and Earthquake. Different scenarios included different scene sounds and animations to add an immersive experience. The application was developed using the Unity Game engine platform which is commonly used by some developers in developing 2D, 3D games especially for developing simulation games or applications. The 3D models that have been presented in the application were manually created in an open- source 3D development software which is the Blender 3d software. The development was able to script and program using the C# programming language compiled in Microsoft Visual Studio Community Edition 2019.

The evaluation process was done in an online procedure using Google Form. This is because, amidst the research development, a pandemic known as the Covid-19 hits the whole world, and the face-to-face evaluation process was not recommended due to the threat in the spread of the virus. The online evaluation had been the safest way to conduct a survey for the completion of the study. The survey includes the overall description of the application and with the Android Package (APK) file and the sample video of the developed system for easy evaluation.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were derived after completing the testing and survey.

The system was successfully designed such that: a) it can simulate natural calamities that are commonly experienced inside a building such as fire-breakout, typhoon, and earthquake; b) indicates Basic Practices Infographics mandated by NDRRMP as an object within the simulation; c) simulates real time evacuation procedure using A* algorithm; and d) provides general evacuation practices based on selected disaster.

The system was successfully developed using the following tools: a) Unity real-time development platform for developing the virtual reality simulation; b) Blender for creating 3D models and infrastructure; c) Photoshop CS6 and for creating graphic design; and d) C# Programming Language in developing the system.

Test results showed that the application is functional in terms of reliability, usability, and portability. Conforming to the ISO 25010 Software evaluation instrument, the application was evaluated “Excellent”.

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